

Micropollutants fate in the water environment from sources to humans: integrated risk assessment and targeted mitigation strategies in a one-health approach

A. Desca, J. Ianes*, L. Penserini*, B. Cantoni*, M. Antonelli*

* Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (DICA) - Environmental Section, Politecnico Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

Abstract

Micropollutants pose significant challenges to the sustainable management of water resources due to the complexity of the water system. In fact, insufficient removal efficiencies in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and untreated wastewater discharged during wet weather events contribute to their persistence in receiving water bodies. Agricultural (re)use further exacerbates challenges, transferring pollutants to soils and crops and impacting both environmental and human health. Receiving waters are also used for drinking water production, requiring a wise management to minimize impacts on consumers' health. Variability in hydrological conditions, such as wet weather events and prolonged dry periods, increasingly relevant in the future due to climate change, amplifies these challenges, necessitating mitigation interventions, which can be targeted through an integrated risk assessment. We propose a One Health framework to comprehensively evaluate the risks posed by micropollutants across interconnected compartments, including industrial discharges, urban overflows, WWTPs, receiving water bodies, and agricultural systems. To ensure acceptable risk levels throughout the system, targeted interventions were assessed, such as the implementation of storage tanks to manage flood events and the enhancement of advanced treatment units in WWTPs. By integrating these strategies, this approach demonstrates how coordinated actions can effectively mitigate risks under multiple conditions, providing a robust and sustainable foundation for addressing environmental and human health challenges in complex water systems.

Keywords

combined sewer overflows, emerging contaminants, quaternary treatment, adsorption, ozonation, wastewater reuse

INTRODUCTION

Conventional and emerging micropollutants represent a challenge in water management due to their increasing detection across water systems worldwide. These compounds include a wide variety of synthetic chemicals, such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS), alkylphenols, and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs). Despite their presence at low concentrations (ng L^{-1} to $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), micropollutants can have significant adverse impacts on both ecosystems and human health, through drinking water and crops consumption. However, relevant uncertainties remain due to knowledge gaps in their release, environmental behavior, and toxicological effects. Managing water quality in urban water systems is particularly complex, as these systems encompass multiple pollutant sources, pathways, and receptors. Urban micropollutants originate from various sources, including point sources as municipal wastewater treatment plant discharges, as well as non-point sources such as stormwater runoff, leading to their accumulation in surface water and groundwater. In fact, when the sewer system capacity is exceeded during rainfalls, combined sewer overflows and bypass release untreated mixtures of wastewater and stormwater directly into surface waters [1]. In addition, agricultural activities also contribute significantly, as pesticides and fertilizers leach into surface water through runoff. Furthermore, the direct or indirect reuse of reclaimed wastewater for irrigation can transfer micropollutants to edible crops, potentially posing risks to human health [2]. Not less important is the impact of water sources contamination in case of drinking [3] or recreational uses. To address the complexity of micropollutant dynamics and ensure an effective environmental-human protection in a One Health perspective, an integrated approach is essential, encompassing comprehensive monitoring, analysis of multiple sources, and advanced fate modeling frameworks [4].

Our goal is to explore the potential of integrated risk assessment procedures for prioritizing micropollutants and compartments to be monitored in urban water systems, and targeting the mitigation strategies that maximize the overall expected risk reduction. Based on the outputs of the integrated risk assessment, (i) preventive approaches can be preferred for selected micropollutants, and/or (ii) mitigation actions can be designed to reduce specific micropollutants in selected water flows.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The developed risk assessment procedure includes several steps. Firstly, the analyzed system boundaries were defined, to consider the compartments and the contaminants involved in the process, from sources to the final endpoint (whether it is the environment or human health). A schematic overview is reported in Figure 1. As for the exposure assessment step, micropollutants concentration data were collected from the literature for each compartment of interest. Additional modeling of micropollutant fate was used to predict their concentrations at the endpoint knowing the concentrations in each source. Then, in the hazard assessment step, the toxicological characterization for each micropollutant was retrieved from the literature. Finally, exposure and hazard assessment steps were combined in the risk characterization step, to quantitatively estimate environmental or human health risk for micropollutants in different compartments.

Figure 1: Conceptual scheme of the integrated urban water system, indicating the main families of micropollutants and the compartments involved, with the proposed risk reduction measures.

As for the environmental risk assessment, the Risk Quotient (RQ) or the Risk Quotient for antibiotic resistance development (RQ_{ARB}) were estimated as the ratio between environmental concentration (MEC) and the Predicted No-Effect Concentration (PNEC), or the Predicted No-Effect Concentration for the antibiotic resistance development in bacteria ($PNEC_{ARB}$). Equations are as follows:

$$RQ = \frac{MEC}{PNEC} \quad (1)$$

$$RQ_{ARB} = \frac{MEC}{PNEC_{ARB}} \quad (2)$$

As for human health risk assessment, the Benchmark Quotient (BQ) was calculated as the contaminant exposure concentration (C_{EXP}), typically originating from crop or drinking water consumption, divided by its reference dose (RfD), as follows:

$$BQ = \frac{C_{EXP}}{RfD} \quad (3)$$

Risk values (RQ or BQ) lower than 0.1 indicates the absence of appreciable concern, between 0.1 and 1 indicates that further investigation might be warranted, and higher than 1 indicates the presence of a risk. The proposed procedure included uncertainty analyses to account for knowledge gaps, input data uncertainties and temporal-spatial variabilities, and modeling uncertainties to provide decision-makers with the confidence level of the risk estimation. This was done through Monte-Carlo

simulations by building the probabilistic distributions of the input variables and propagating such uncertainty distributions in the risk characterization step.

Regarding the actions aimed at reducing risks, focusing on the role of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in both dry and wet weather, the following interventions were proposed (Figure 1):

- *Storage systems for Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) and WWTP by-pass (BP)*, to prevent untreated discharges during wet weather events, and reduce PAHs load and heavy metals to water bodies, with stored water treated during normal operations [5].
- *Enhanced oxidation processes and adsorption on activated carbon in WWTPs*, to effectively remove residual micropollutants after biological process, improving treatment efficiency [4,6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integrated risk assessment allows to build management scenarios to be quantitatively compared in terms of residual risk for the environment or for human health, allowing for a final ranking of the scenarios based on their effectiveness. Examples are reported in Figure 2 referring to discharges during wet weather and reclaimed wastewater aimed to be reused for crop irrigation, that can result in the release of a variety of contaminants into the environment.

As shown in Figure 2a, the environmental chronic risks posed by CSOs represent the highest threat to surface water, followed by BP and effluents (EFF), indicating that mitigation strategies should prioritize CSOs. In addition, Figure 2b illustrates the evolution of investigated parameters in CSOs over time, highlighting a growing focus on emerging contaminants and micropollutants. The implementation of water storage basins can provide significant benefits, enabling the management of discharges during wet weather conditions, reducing untreated water releases into the environment, and subsequently directing the stored water to WWTPs during dry weather conditions. Reducing CSO-related discharges can lower PAHs risks by up to 77% [5].

Figure 2: (a) RQ for benzo(a)pyrene (BaP), example of PAH, for each discharge type from an integrated water system. (b) Temporal evolution of parameters analyzed in CSOs (2002 to 2021).

Figure 3a offers an insight in case of the indirect reuse of reclaimed wastewater in agriculture: in this situation both environmental risk (effluent released in the surface water) and human health (consumption of irrigated crops) risk co-exist even if they are often assessed individually. Estimated human health risk is substantially lower than the warning threshold (BQ equal to 0.1) for the three pharmaceuticals and three antibiotics considered, suggesting that the presence of these micropollutants in reclaimed wastewater does not pose a risk to human health. However, both the environmental risk and the risk of antibiotic resistance development significantly contribute to the overall risk, suggesting the need for additional treatments. The removal efficiency associated with the adoption of quaternary treatments (e.g., ozonation combined with activated carbon) in WWTPs enables the achievement of high values for the targeted micropollutants, as shown in Figure 3b for carbamazepine and diclofenac, especially for ozonation.

Figure 3: (a) Risk indices distributions for human health, environmental, and antibiotic resistance development risk for carbamazepine (CBZ), diclofenac (DCF), ibuprofen (IBU), metronidazole (MET), sulfamethoxazole (SMX), trimethoprim (TMP); MET concentration in crops was always below the limit of detection, making the human health risk not quantifiable. (b) Removal efficiency of quaternary treatments (O3: ozonation, GAC: granular activated carbon, PAC: powdered activated carbon) for CBZ and DCF.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed approach stresses the paramount importance of the One Health approach for an effective protection of environmental and human health, since it permits to comprehensively address multiple risks in the complex water system. By targeting mitigation strategies through their impacts across interconnected compartments, the proposed approach provides a robust tool supporting sustainable water management within present and future challenges.

The research is being funded by PNRR MUR - M4C2 Project “Return: Natural, man-made and environmental risks” (Project ID: PE-0000005, CUP D43C22003030002).

REFERENCES

- [1] Ianes J., Cantoni B., Polesel F., Remigi E.U., Vezzaro L., Antonelli M. (2024). Monitoring (micro-)pollutants in wastewater treatment plants: comparing discharges in wet- and dry-weather. *Environmental Research*, 263, 120132
- [2] Penserini, L., Cantoni, B., Gabrielli, M., Sezenna, E., Saponaro, S., Antonelli, M., 2023. *An integrated human health risk assessment framework for alkylphenols due to drinking water and crops' food consumption*. *Chemosphere* 325, 138259.
- [3] Cantoni B., Ianes J., Bertolo B., Ziccardi S., Maffini F., Antonelli M. (2024). Adsorption on activated carbon combined with ozonation for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern in drinking water. *J. Environ. Manage.*, 350, 119537.
- [4] Penserini, L., Cantoni, B., Antonelli, M., 2024. *Modelling the impacts generated by reclaimed wastewater reuse in agriculture: From literature gaps to an integrated risk assessment in a One Health perspective*. *Journal of Environmental Management* 371, 122715
- [5] Ianes, J., Cantoni, B., Remigi, E.U., Polesel, F., Vezzaro, L., Antonelli, M., 2023. A stochastic approach for assessing the chronic environmental risk generated by wet-weather events from integrated urban wastewater systems. *Environ. Sci: Water Res. Technol.* 9, 3174-3190.
- [6] Ianes, J., Cantoni, B., Scana F., Delli Compagni R., Polesel F., Remigi E.U., Vezzaro L., Antonelli, M., 2024. *Implications of the transition towards water-wise approaches in urban areas: Elucidating the risk from micropollutants release*. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 12, 112676